

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Applications of the CRISPR-Cas-based technology to correct aneuploid and segmental aneuploid cells: The road from lab to clinic

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Abstract

Genetic disorders pose an enormous health threat to human public health. There are presently no disorder-reducing therapy options. The purpose of this article is to review the latest applications and prospects of Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR) and CRISPR-associated proteins (Cas) (CRISPR-Cas) system in the treatment of human chromosomal disorders. One of the reasons for choosing this topic is because of the lack of related literature. In this review, we first briefly describe a human chromosomal disorder and then outline the molecular architecture and mechanistic basis of CRISPR-Cas9 for its treatment. Then, successful stories in this field are described. The process begins with identifying and cleaving particular sequences on the extra copy of a chromosome. This activates a repair response that guides the cell to eradicate the chromosome without harming the other healthy chromosomes. Thus, instead of editing single genes, scientists can effectively remove a chromosomal abnormality entirely, restoring normal gene expression and cellular function. Although the CRISPR-Cas method has operated well for curing chromosomal disorders in lab settings, the clinical applications are years away because several mechanistic questions have to be answered. Before clinical applications, the methods could be tested *in vivo* in animal models and adapted to become a keystone for future cell-replacement therapies. Challenges and limitations have to be addressed by geneticists, bioethicists, and policymakers before human translation.

Keywords: Aneuploidy; Chromosomal Disorders; Chromosome Elimination; CRISPR-Cas Therapy; Segmental Aneuploid; Trisomy

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Graphical Abstract

1. Introduction

1.1. What are CRISPR/Cas Systems?

In 2013, the CRISPR-Cas system's multi-genome editing abilities made possible powerful applications in basic science, biotechnology, and medicine.[1] By using a single effector protein and a customizable single-guide RNA (sgRNA), CRISPR-Cas9 surpasses former engineered nucleases such as zinc-finger nucleases (ZFNs) and transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs) in simplicity and flexibility.[2] Several studies have shown that the CRISPR system, as a gene programming instrument, can increase the gene diagnosis capability.[3][4]

A variety of the CRISPR-Cas effectors (Figure 1 and Table 1) have been innovated as technology advances and developments enable researchers to join computation and experiments.[5] The Cas 9 protein consists of two functional lobes: the recognition (REC) lobe and the nuclease (NUC) lobe.[5] Attached to the REC lobe is the NUC lobe, which shelters and protects the dual nuclease domains, human umbilical vein endothelium cells (HuvC) and HNH (named for its conserved histidine-asparagine-histidine catalytic triad), which regulate the endonucleolytic cleavage of the DNA strands.[6] The HNH domain shows target-dependent activation (i.e., remains catalytically inactive until accurate base pairing between the gRNA and target DNA is formed) [7] and cleaves the complementary strand of the DNA duplex. Together, the HNH domain aligns with the target strand and cuts the DNA in a coordinated manner with RuvC, leading to a blunt-ended DSB. The REC lobe domain facilitates gRNA binding and conformational regulation, allowing the surveillance complex to accomplish high-fidelity recognition of the DNA substrate. A key turning point came about when researchers revealed that crRNA and trans-activating crRNA (tracrRNA) could be joined into a sgRNA, producing a simplified but highly effective system for leading Cas9 to specific DNA sequences.[8] The precise targeting of Cas9 is further imposed by the protospacer adjacent motif (PAM), a small conserved DNA sequence, located directly downstream of the target site.[9]

Figure 1 Comparison of the structural properties and the target of CRISPR/Cas9, CRISPR/Cas12, and CRISPR/Cas13. Abbreviations: dsDNA: Double-Stranded DNA; ssDNA: Single-Stranded DNA; ssRNA: Single-Stranded RNA. Source: [10, 11]

Table 1 Comparison of the functional properties of CRISPR/Cas9, CRISPR/Cas12, and CRISPR/Cas13. *

Aspect	CRISPR-Cas9	CRISPR-Cas12	CRISPR-Cas13
Target	dsDNA	ssDNA, dsDNA	ssRNA only
Protospacer restrictions	PAM	PAM	PFS
Spacer size	16-24 nt	16-24 nt	22-35 nt
Pre-crRNA processing	No	Yes	No
DNA recognition	sgRNA (crRNA in complex with tracrRNA)	crRNA	crRNA
tracrRNA	Yes	No	No
Cleavage pattern	Blunt-ended DSB	Sticky-ended DSB	Degraded RNA
Characteristics	-No collateral cleavage -No secondary structure restrictions	-Collateral cleavage -No secondary structure restrictions	-Collateral cleavage -Secondary structure restrictions
Application	Gene editing nucleic acid detection	Gene editing nucleic acid detection	RNA knockout nucleic acid detection
Active clinical trials	Yes	Yes	No

* Abbreviations: crRNA: CRISPR RNA; DSB: Double Strand Breaks; dsDNA: Double-Stranded DNA; nt: Nucleotide; PAM: Protospacer Adjacent Motif; PFS: Protospacer Flanking Site; ssDNA: Single-Stranded DNA; ssRNA: Single-Stranded RNA; tracrRNA: Transactivating RNA. Data extracted from:[10][11]

One of the landmark events was the introduction of nucleases like Cas12 and Cas13 (Figure 1), which bind to crRNA targets, into nucleic acid detection systems. [11][12][13] These nucleases also differ in the cleavage pattern and PAM range. The Cas12 nuclease possesses unique enzymological features and can detect nucleic acids by cutting of surrounding single-stranded DNA (ssDNA).[14] On the other hand, Cas13 is an RNA-guided RNA-targeting endonuclease. Cas13a's specificity for RNA, not including DNA changes, makes it a fascinating tool for transient knockout (KO) in research and possible therapeutic applications for diseases involving RNA.[5] The discovery of the trans-cleavage mechanism of these enzymes made them a promising and powerful proposal for the next generation CRISPR-based diagnostics (CRISPR-Dx). While Cas13's RNA specificity is perfect for transient KO and diagnostics, its collateral cleavage can sometimes lead to off-target RNA degradation, restraining its therapeutic potential.[15][16]

The main functions of the CRISPR-Cas could be summarized as follows: Targeting a definite sequence and cutting the relevant site, producing double-strand breaks (DSBs). The generated breaks are resolved by alternative and competing repair routes, largely error-prone non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) and high-reliability homology-directed repair (HDR).[17] The NHEJ-facilitated insertion or deletion incidences for gene disruption have proven invaluable. However,

the therapeutic goal of precise gene correction dictates the enhancement of HDR efficacy in mammalian cells, where this pathway is essentially limited by cell-cycle restrictions and enzymatic competition. The HDR is predominantly active during the S and G2 phases of the cell cycle once a sister chromatid is available as a template.[18] Despite its precision, HDR is inherently less effective in somatic cells owing to cell cycle limitations and pathway competition, restricting its usefulness in therapeutic and research contexts that require accuracy.[17] To overcome these limitations, several approaches have emerged to encourage HDR over NHEJ, thus improving the efficacy and fidelity of CRISPR-Cas9-based genome editing (GE). Many of these strategies, though potent, may cause unwanted genome-wide perturbations or increase the risk of chromosomal rearrangements because of excessive end resection or long repair activity.[19] Nevertheless, these approaches hold huge promise for applications in gene therapy, particularly when limited to ex vivo contexts such as patient-derived stem cells [20]. Recent advances in HDR-stimulating and NHEJ-overcoming strategies, describing developing solutions to CRISPR-Cas9's systemic drawbacks, can be found in recent reviews.[8][11]

1.2. What are the Genetic Disorders?

Genetic disorders include a broad spectrum of diseases. Mutations that occur in the genome of an organism can be classified into two major classes: gene mutations and chromosomal mutations. [21] The gene mutation is a change of the nucleotide sequence of a gene in the DNA, whereas a chromosomal mutation is a change of the structure or number of chromosomes. The effect of chromosomal mutations is greater than that of gene mutations because the degree of mutation in chromosomal mutations is high; only one gene is affected in the first, while several genes are affected in the second,[21] leading to carcinogenesis, morbidity, or mortality.[22] The influence of genetic chromosomal mutations on human health can be great on many things throughout the body, including growth and development, and physical appearance.

Chromosomal mutations mostly result from errors in mitosis or meiosis.[21] There are four forms of structural chromosomal alterations: deletions, duplications, inversions, and translocations. Translocations involve the interchange of pieces of chromosomes between non-homologous chromosomes. Duplication is the generation of extra copies of a chromosome segment. Broken chromosomal portions are rotated 180° and again inserted into the same site of the chromosome during inversions. Pericentric inversions contain a centromere. In the paracentric inversions, the inverting segment does not involve the centromere.

The numerical chromosome alterations are called aneuploidy, defined as having in a single cell one or more extra or missing chromosomes. Lacking one of the chromosomes is known as monosomy ($2n-1$), while gaining an extra chromosome is called trisomy ($2n+1$).

1.3. CRISPR/Cas9-Based Therapy

Genetic diseases often lead to substantial medical and economic burdens on patients and healthcare systems. Major significant advances in GE approaches to correct single-gene errors of rare monogenic disorders have been reported in the last decade, starting with in vitro experiments and advancing to in vivo studies and clinical trials.[23] In comparison, only a few efforts have been devoted to genetically correcting the improper dosage of genes for a whole chromosome in aneuploid cells.[23] This is because each chromosome carries hundreds of genes, and the addition or deletion of even a single chromosome disrupts the delicate balance of gene products in cells. Earlier reported methods to precisely delete a whole particular human chromosome or remove most of a chromosome were laborious and extremely inefficient. These methods can be classified into two main classes: nuclease-based and nuclease-dCas9 strategies to tether a definite protein to a chromosome of desire.[24] Nuclease-mediated strategies include the Cas9 system with one or several Chromosome-specific sgRNAs, where one or many DNA DSBs are produced in the arm,[23][24][25] or the (peri-centromeric) region of the targeted chromosome,[26] causing total or partial loss of the targeted chromosome. Other such strategies include a mixture of centromere-proximal and centromere-distal DSBs [27] or artificial telomere sequence integration into the peri-centromere.[27][28]

Targeted entire chromosome deletion could be accomplished by four main approaches:

- Introducing an oppositely oriented locus of X over P (loxP) sites, which are specific 34 bp DNA sequences utilized in genetic engineering, into the intended chromosome, followed by a site-specific recombinase technology.[29] Incorporation of the inverted loxP into the chromosome was carried out by traditional gene targeting, CRISPR/Cas9 nickase system, and TALEN technology.[29][30] Chromosomes with inverted loxP locations can be converted to unstable acentric and dicentric chromosomes in a Cre recombinase-dependent

fashion. The unstable chromosome will be eliminated during cell division, thus enhancing the exclusion of the target chromosome having the inverted loxP sites. [22]

- Introducing a *Thymidine Kinase and Neomycin (TKNEO)* resistant transgene, a specific fusion gene utilized in genetic engineering for positive or negative antibiotic selection, into one copy of a chromosome of interest, followed by drug selection of chromosome-elimination clones via spontaneous chromosome deletion.[31]
- Both of these strategies are conventional methods for GE that demand two-step manipulation and give low yields of chromosome-deleted cells, and are therefore inappropriate for in vivo studies.[23]
- Using ZFN-based knock-in (KI) of the *X-inactive specific transcript (XIST)* gene, located on the human X chromosome, to silence one copy of chromosome 21.[32] This procedure added another potential chromosomal therapy for Down Syndrome (DS), allowing the accurate and efficient insertion of the *XIST* gene into chromosome 21 in Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells (iPSCs).
- Using multiple gRNAs of the CRISPR/Cas9 system CRISPR/Cas9 system for initiating multiple DNA DSBs into the target location are designed for a whole region of the target and consequently eliminate extra chromosomes.[23][24]

By suppressing the cell's intrinsic DNA repair mechanisms, scientists expanded the efficacy of removing the additional chromosome. Their findings indicated that this process restored natural gene expression and cellular function in edited cells. Genome editing utilizing CRISPR/Cas9 reportedly brings great loss of entire chromosomes.[33] Whole chromosome loss is usually discussed in the context of the severe and potentially fatal side effects of CRISPR/Cas9-mediated gene therapy attempts.[34]

"Trisomic rescue" was the first time the elimination of a whole chromosome was achieved using CRISPR. Although research directed toward getting rid of supernumerary chromosomes from trisomic cells is limited,[35] several success stories have been reported in the literature. The emerging biomedical application of CRISPR systems in this field is outlined in Figure 2 and will be summarized in the sections that follow.

2. Methods

This review article used the major databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science to search literature published from 2005 to 2025. The keywords used in different combinations were "Aneuploidy", "CRISPR", "chromosome disorder", "chromosome syndrome", "genome editing", and "therapy". Following PRISMA guidelines, 281 papers were vigorously evaluated. Articles published in None-English-language as well those with insufficient data were excluded. Only 121 articles fulfilled the inclusion criteria following application of the exclusion criteria (Articles published in None-English-language or having insufficient data). The selected studies were organized into thematic groupings covering specific chromosome syndrome.

3. Results

3.1. Down Syndrome

Human trisomy 21, responsible for DS, is the most frequent genetic cause of cognitive impairment and continues to be a key focus for researchers. In about 95% of the cases, it occurs when an individual has an extra copy of chromosome 21 in every cell of the body, where there should normally only be two copies. Down syndrome is the only survivable trisomy condition. It is one of the most frequent genetic disorders in humans, affecting about 1 in 700 live births.[36] Although this condition can be easily diagnosed early in development by genetic testing for aneuploidy, many treatments or modifying practices are symptomatic interferences.[37]

Figure 2 Therapeutic gene editing using CRISPR/Cas9 offers theoretically promising avenues for treating chromosomal disorders by correcting the underlying genetic defect. Source: Author's design

In general, the exact set of genes causing the clinical phenotypes in DS, which is influenced by the increase in chromosome copy number, is mostly unknown. But it has been reported [22] that three copies of the *RUNX1*, *ETS2*, and *ERG* genes on chromosome 21 co-activate with somatic *GATA1* mutations on the X chromosome elevate the risk of leukemia in DS. TALEN-based elimination of the *GATA1* mutation in DS patient-stemmed human iPSCs (hiPSCs) restored the right hematopoiesis even in the presence of trisomy 21.[38] For clinical applications of this procedure, further improvements are needed for the complete silencing of the desired chromosome 21.

In HeLa cells with three copies of chromosome 21, integration of the *GFP* and *Herpes Simplex Virus-thymidine kinase (HSV-tk)* gene holder encased by two inverted loxP positions on the homologous arms of chromosome 21 by homologous recombination following CRISPR/Cas9 system-mediated DNA nicking, produced unstable acentric and dicentric chromosomes for chromosome 21 elimination and a final normal 46 genotype.[22] A similar result was obtained by applying a CRISPR/Cas9 approach-mediated chromosomal deletion using two sgRNAs targeting repetitive sequences on chromosome 21 in the DS-iPSCs, converting trisomy 21 to disomy at a frequency of approximately 15%.[22]

It was found that even when recombination happens between homologous chromosomes, every copy of chromosome 21 typically has unique gRNA targets. This feature offers the advantage of targeting only one of the three chromosome copies. CRISPR/Cas9-based targeted chromosome deletion dramatically altered researchers' ability to produce disease models in various organisms, such as non-human primates. Moreover, this strategy would provide a possible therapeutic strategy to cure aneuploidy diseases, including DS, Klinefelter syndrome (XXY), and Jacobs syndrome (XYY). [31][32][39] Yet, the off-target effects (OTEs) of the CRISPR/Cas9 system and the efficiency of aneuploidy rescue applied in this approach should be assessed and developed for use in basic and clinical research on aneuploidy disorders.

Furthermore, researchers applied a ZFN-mediated strategy to KI the *XIST* gene on the *Dual-specificity Tyrosine Phosphorylation Regulated Kinase 1A (DYRK1A)* gene locus of chromosome 21, causing Barr body development to silence the additional copy of chromosome 21 in DS-iPSCs.[22] Remarkably, the trisomy-biased chromosome loss through iPSC reprogramming was also enforced in DS iPSC cells, which lost the additional copy of chromosome 21. Interestingly, the long-term path of DS-iPSCs with trisomy 21 also led to T-Cell Lymphoma (TCL), thereby correcting the karyotype.[22] However, the mechanisms that cause TCL remain unclear.

An approach that combines CRISPR-Cas9-based chromosome tagging and Microcell-Mediated Chromosome Transfer (MMCT) from hiPSCs as chromosome donor cells directly to other hiPSCs as chromosome recipient cells.[40] This procedure allows the more straightforward production of hyperaneuploidy disease models, genetic chromosome disorder models, and cells containing familial chromosomes. This strategy included tagging chromosome 21 and chromosome Y by CRISPR-Cas9 and moving human/mouse Artificial chromosome, chromosome 21, chromosome X, and chromosome Y, for which no previous reports confirm full-length introduction. This approach enables the study of rare diseases and promises to offer new perceptions into early developmental mechanisms by establishing a comprehensive set of important chromosomes/regions in hiPSCs.

It was found that an overdose of genes in aneuploid cells could be adjusted by the insertion of a bulky, inducible *XIST* transgene into the targeted chromosome to silence one copy of it.[32] However, the efficacy of the targeted insertion was very low, and some genes may have escaped the inactivation process. A new application of the CRISPR/Cas9 tool was reported, (23) which involves the selective removal of a single specific chromosome by multiple DNA cleavages on the intended chromosome in cultured cells, embryos, and in vivo tissues. The cleavages made by these researchers were produced by a single sgRNA or two sgRNAs that recognized multiple chromosome-specific locations, or by a mixture of 14 sgRNAs, with each recognizing one specific locus. Thus, the CRISPR/Cas9 approach proved its capacity to eliminate human chromosome 21 (hChr21) in hiPSCs with trisomy 21, offering a novel method to generate animal models and treatments for aneuploidy.

It is known that Down patients with partial trisomy and/or mosaic form showed a 1.6 Mb vital region on chromosome 21q22 with maximum level of transcription in DS.[41] This region is called the DS Critical Region (DSCR). Most of the genes found in DSCR are linked to the development of the brain and play an important role in learning and cognitive activities, and loss of them causes neuropathological issues in DS. Even some recent investigations confined the DSCR region to a very short distance, duplicated in all DS patients.[42] Therefore, consideration of a smaller number of genes, which are more specific for DS phenotypes, appears to be more logical for alterations to correct adverse phenotypes.

Based on previous studies about more principal genes that have a higher impact in generating DS clinical manifestations (Figure 4), a method that can significantly lessen the main influences and clinical features in DS was suggested.[34] Two different CRISPR/Cas9 systems were applied concurrently in a protein-based delivery technique to both the brain cell culture and the DS mouse model. The first is a gene deletion approach and includes a Cas9 protein + two distinct sgRNAs for cutting off two ends of the DSCR region in chromosome 21, and the second involves a Cas9 protein + a sgRNA + a template dsDNA to excise a nonfunctional region of the centromere-proximal half of 21q. After that, the latter region was replaced by a newly planned DNA construct, which included some main genes in chromatin remodeling and epigenetic effects for the inactivation of one additional chromosome 21 (Figure 3, Table 2).

Figure 3 The devised DNA construct for substituting specific, nonfunctional locations on chromosome 21. This comprises an enhancer for brain cells special promoter (i.e., *MECP2* promoter), *MECP2* expression promoter, *XIST* gene as a major epigenetic modifier factor for causing inactivation on the related chromosome, and a long non-coding RNA gene like *L1* gene on behalf of a specific element for enhancing *Xist* RNA function. Also, an RNA polymerase terminator gene would be required to regulate the transcription activities. * *L1*: Like1; *MECP2*: Methyl CpG binding protein 2; *XIST*: X-inactive specific transcript. Source: Adapted from [43]

In this way, the extra chromosome 21 would be repressed or inactivated by omitting the DSCR region, followed by insertion or KI of the regulatory DNA construct. However, inactivation can be observed in other chromosomes too, since the female's X chromosome is not the only deactivated chromosome example in the human body. Research showed that the inactivation could also occur in males' germ cells as meiotic sex chromosome inactivation (MSCI) form.[44]

Table 2 Expressed and silenced genes on extra chromosome 21 in Down Syndrome patients.

Gene region*	To be expressed	To be silenced
<i>MECP2</i> enhancer	Enhancer for transcription from the <i>MECP2</i> promoter	-
<i>MECP2</i> expression promoter	Selective expression of desired genes in neurons	-
<i>XIST</i>	Aggregates histone changes, which inhibit transcription	-
<i>L1</i>	Overexpression of this gene is implicated in <i>Xist</i> RNA dispersal along the chromosome.	-
RNA polymerase terminator	Termination of transcription of desired genes	-
All other genes: <i>DSCR1, RCAN1, PCP4, TTC3, MNB, SOD, ETS2, SIM2, DYRK1, DSCAM</i> , Other <i>DSCR</i> genes, Genes within <i>BCE1</i> and <i>MX1</i>	-	Critical regions involved in DS

* *BCE1*: Beta-Secretase 1; *DSCAM*: DS Cell Adhesion Molecule; *DSCR*: Down syndrome critical region; *DYRK1*: Dual-specificity tyrosine phosphorylation-regulated kinase 1; *ETS2*: Erythroblast Transformation Specific 2; *L1*: Like1; *MECP2*: Methyl CpG binding protein 2; *MNB*: Minibrain; *PCP4*: Purkinje cell protein 4; *MX1*: Myxoma 1; *RCAN1*: Regulator of Calcineurin 1; *SIM2*: single-minded 2; *SOD*: Superoxide dismutase; *TTC3*: Tetratricopeptide Repeat Domain 3; *XIST*: X-inactive specific transcript. Source: Data extracted from:[43].

As discussed above, CRISPR/Cas9 can specifically cleave assigned sites in a DNA sequence through the direction of sgRNA. CRISPR/Cas9 with specially designed sgRNAs can target repetitive sequences and break all the repeats in the chromosome. As a result, the chromosome would be damaged beyond the limits of the intrinsic cell repair. Consequently, the targeted chromosome cannot join in the DNA replication during cell division, and will vanish in the offspring.

Using CRISPR-Cas9, scientists successfully removed extra copies of chromosome 21 in DS cell lines, reestablishing normal gene expression.[35] This “surgical” procedure is carried out in utero (in the uterus during embryonic life). What makes this breakthrough specifically groundbreaking is that researchers achieved this chromosomal correction not just in lab-grown PSCs, but also in skin fibroblasts derived from a child with DS. The technique was capable of identifying and precisely targeting the duplicated chromosome, making certain that after removal, each cell kept one copy from each parent rather than two identical copies. The treated cells reverted from trisomy (three chromosomes) to disomy (two chromosomes), restoring normal karyotypes. The results were certified using standard tools in cytogenetics, such as FISH, Short Tandem Repeat (STR) profiling, and the G-banding technique. Edited cells returned to normal patterns of protein production. They also displayed better survival levels in certain tests, suggesting that the surplus genetic burden was successfully alleviated. In follow-up tests, investigators [35] examined how gene activity differed after eliminating the extra chromosome. The corrected cells developed slightly faster and had a shorter doubling time compared to the untreated trisomy cells, suggesting that getting rid of the extra chromosome may relieve the biological stress that reduces cell growth. This idea is supported by the finding that the corrected cells also generated fewer reactive oxygen species, which are harmful byproducts associated with cell damage and aging, reflecting perfected mitochondrial function and an overall boost in cell fitness.

Furthermore, the genes linked to nervous system development were dialed up, while those tied to metabolism became less active. This change in gene expression may perhaps explain how fixing the chromosomal imbalance influences the cell’s general behavior. It also strengthens earlier results that extra copies of chromosome 21 disturb brain growth during early fetal development.

Although promising, the technique is not yet ready for use in living organisms and clinical applications, as it may also change the remaining chromosomes. But researchers suppose that similar strategies could eventually be used in neurons and glial cells or other tissues, paving the way for potential future treatments for persons with DS. Since the presence of a third copy of a chromosome has effects on many things in the body, including growth and development as well as physical appearance, the question remains, “Would a person who underwent this therapy begin changing physically?”

3.2. Edwards Syndrome

Edwards syndrome (ES) or Trisomy 18, is the second most common autosomal trisomy abnormality after trisomy 21 (DS).[45] In rare situations, trisomy 18 may come from a biological parent (through balanced translocation). If a family already has had one child with triplicate chromosome 18, the doctor may suggest having genetic testing to evaluate the chances of having another child with a similar disorder.[46]

Children born with ES require specialized care to deal with their unique symptoms soon after they are born. Medical science has not discovered a cure for ES.[45] However, in some cases, surgical mediation may be needed to address particular health issues linked with ES. Scientists are exploring conventional therapy strategies for ES that have concentrated on managing symptoms instead of directly targeting the main genetic cause.

CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing technique holds great promise in dealing with ES at a molecular level. It enables researchers to exactly modify DNA sequences and possibly correct the genetic errors linked to the syndrome. Although still in the infancy stages, CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing sets up an era for the treatment and intervention with ES. By exactly modifying the defective genes responsible for the disorder, these therapies can provide more efficient and personalized treatment options. It has been determined that CRISPR/Cas9 can be utilized to target and remove an allele-specific chromosome in trisomy 18 embryos.[47]

Recently, a Japanese research team at Kyoto University and the RIKEN Center used the same strategy employed for chromosome 21 elimination to delete the extra chromosome 18 trisomic cells.[48] Utilizing the intrinsic cellular repair mechanisms, specifically designed gRNAs in CRISPR-Cas9 to target, bind repetitive sequences unique to chromosome 18, triggering Cas9-induced breaks. The engineered CRISPR-Cas9 systems were delivered via viral vectors to remove the additional chromosome in *in vitro* cell cultures. Though still in the experimental stages, CRISPR-Cas9 GE opens up an era of potential for the treatment and prevention of ES. Most treatments such as these would be performed by 20 weeks of gestation since most duplications appear in the first stage of uterine development.

3.3. Klinefelter Syndrome

Klinefelter syndrome (KS) is a common congenital disease that results when a male at birth has at least one extra X chromosome added to a normal male karyotype, 46, XY.[49] Around 90% of males with KS have the 47, XXY karyotype. The XXY aneuploidy is the most prevalent disorder of sex chromosomes in humans, with a prevalence of one in 600 males.[49] The additional X chromosome in 47, XXY, results occasionally from either meiotic nondisjunction when a chromosome fails to segregate during the first or second division of gametogenesis or from mitotic nondisjunction in the emerging zygote.[50] If the diagnosis is not performed prenatally, the 47, XXY males may display a variety of subtle clinical signs, such as smaller testicles, which are unable to produce normal levels of the hormone testosterone.

There are presently no gene therapy options for KS. However, there are some ongoing or planned clinical trials searching for the use of GE technologies such as CRISPR-Cas9 to repair or delete genes on the extra X chromosome. It was reported [51] that the Y chromosome could be eliminated in embryonic stem cells (ESCs) and zygotes by CRISPR/Cas9-based GE. Similarly, the Y chromosome completely deleted by multiple CRISPR/Cas9-based DNA cuts on the targeted chromosome in ESCs, cells *in vivo*, and zygotes with high efficacy.[23] It was demonstrated that using the same strategy, one of two homologous X chromosomes, which is characteristic of KS (XXY), in mouse embryos with the XX karyotype could be effectively removed.[52]

The majority of the chromosome-specific repeated sequences are found in non-coding regions, and thus these side effects could be reduced by targeting the non-coding DNA sequences within short regions (< 2 kb) without noticeable biological functions.[23] Alternatively, these mutations in the remaining X chromosome (KS) cells could be avoided by using sgRNAs that can target only one of the two or one of the three homologous chromosomes. The Y chromosome could be deleted by using 14 single-target sgRNAs. But, minimizing the number of sgRNAs and improving the efficacy of chromosome removal may make this strategy more applicable. These attempts are still in their experimental stages and have not yet been confirmed for their safety and effectiveness.

During reprogramming KS-modeled XXY mouse primary fibroblasts into iPSCs, aneuploidy was corrected at a rate of approximately 20%.[53] The euploid XY iPSCs produced from the KS model mice differentiated into functional testicular sperm capable of producing the F1 and F2 generation pups.

Unfortunately, GE using CRISPR/Cas9 has been reported to cause enormous chromosome deletions and, rarely, X and autosome entire chromosome elimination.[31][51]

3.4. Turner Syndrome

Turner syndrome (TS), or monosomy X, is the only known viable monosomy. All the autosomal monosomies are lethal. Females with TS have an abnormal karyotype (45, X), reflecting the possession of a single copy of the X chromosome.[54] Numerous significant clinical improvements have been accomplished, covering all specialty fields associated with the care of girls and women with TS.[55]

Currently, there is no effective gene therapy program for TS. The correction of XO to XX, which is uniparental disomy of chromosome X in TS model hiPSCs, has traditionally depended on the occurrence of the uniparental duplication of chromosome X in somatic cell reprogramming,[56] but at a low rate. Because XO could be converted to XX in human fibrosarcoma cells (HT1080), it is inferred that chromosome number correction could be possible for TS's syndrome model hiPSCs.[40]

Other experimental investigations are underway, such as using Artificial chromosome to supplement missing genes on the X chromosome.[57] There are numerous mouse models for aneuploidy disorders, such as the XO mouse for TS. However, many features of patients with TS could not be well repeated in those mouse models, including the two most conventional short stature and premature ovarian failure which affect over 90% of documented patients.[58]

The first report [23] on X chromosome deletion via GE confirmed that the use of the CRISPR/Cas9-mediated multiple DNA cleavages on the targeted chromosome could selectively delete a sex chromosome in cultured cells, embryos, and tissues in vivo. However, these methods require further verification and improvement before they can be applied clinically.

3.5. Fragile X-Chromosome Syndrome

Fragile X syndrome (FXCS) is an inherited intellectual disability that results from the expansion of a congenital trinucleotide CGG repeat within the 5' untranslated region (UTR) of the *Fragile X Mental Retardation 1 (FMR1)* gene on the X chromosome (Figure 4).[59][60] In this case, the *FMR1* gene is methylated and consequently silenced, leading to a lack of a protein (FMRP) that is needed for the normal expansion of neuronal connections. Carriers of the premutation allele have high *FMR1* mRNA amounts but also have a reduced level of the translational efficacy of the *FMR1* encoded protein FMRP.[61]

Figure 4 The X chromosome shows the pinched fragile site, absent in a normal X chromosome. *Fragile X Mental Retardation 1 (FMR1)*, a premutation, contains between 55 and 200 CGG repeats. A cocktail of sgRNAs and purified Cas9 protein is used to target both the upstream and downstream flanking regions of the CGG repeat

The diagnosis of FXCS needs genetic testing to define the number of CGG repeats in the *FMR1* gene. Under normal situations, this number varies between 5 and 40; when the number goes beyond 200, the FXCS will appear. When the number of repeats is between 55 and 200, it is called a premutation. Women with a premutation are likely to have a higher risk of having an affected child.[62] Women with FXCS are frequently less severely affected than men because they have a protective second copy of the *FMR1* gene that is expressed in cells when the full mutation exists in the inactive X chromosome.[61]

Previous studies have indicated that 5-Azacytidine can reverse DNA methylation in the *FMR1*; however, this drug can be toxic, which may limit its therapeutic potential.[63] Furthermore, researchers showed that the dietary factor Ascorbic Acid can reduce this methylation in the *FMR1* locus and lead to an increase in *FMR1* gene expression in FXCS iPSCs and cerebral organoids [64]. The gene therapy program for FXCS is still in the experimental phase and has not yet reached clinical trials. The CRISPR/Cas9 system has quickly proven efficient in correcting Fragile X-Associated Disorders (FXADs).[61][65] More recently, Antisense Oligonucleotide (ASO) therapy has been suggested as a potential novel treatment for FXCS.[66] None of these methods is available to be examined in humans just yet and will need additional research to confirm safety, tolerability, and effectiveness.

The first work applying CRISPR in FXCS was carried out using the CRISPR-Cas9 system to repair the *FMR1* gene by removing the CGG repeats. Two research teams were able to use this system to cut the repeats, activate FMR1 mRNA transcription, and promote FMRP protein expression.[67][68] The first group [67] electroporated hiPSCs harboring an epigenetically silenced full mutation of the *FMR1* allele with plasmid DNA encoding SpCas9 and a gRNA. The gRNA was designed to target 35 bps downstream and 40 bps upstream of the triplet repeat designed to target 35 bps downstream and 40 bps upstream of the triplet repeat. The other group, [68], used a protocol to nucleofect CRISPR plasmids with gRNAs targeting the same sequence to delete the CGG repeats from iPSCs and Human Epidermal Keratinocytes (HEK 293). Full removal of the CGG repeats was reported in iPSCs. Furthermore, a loss of methylation at the promoter after CRISPR-based elimination of the complete mutation CGG repeats, and continuous *FMR1* expression was found after reprogramming the hiPSCs into neuronal cells [67]. With dual guides, the efficiency of deleting CGG repeats reached 20% of the edited iPSCs. Transcriptional reactivation of *FMR1* was stable and persisted for 50 days in culture. The reactivated clonal lines after CRISPR editing had reduced methylation levels at the CpG locations.[68] In contrast, the unedited control clones without reactivation displayed similar methylation degrees as unedited iPSC cells.

The variations in epigenetic adjustments and *FMR1* expression in CGG removed cells were attributed to incomplete DNA remethylation after DNA replication. Due to this, more actively dividing cell types would be likely to undergo more effective *FMR1* reactivation after CRISPR editing of the CGG repeat, whereas nondividing cells will be less susceptible to this demethylation.

Though encouraging, neither the Park study [67] nor the Xie study [68] revealed direct editing in differentiated cells, and therefore the CRISPR/Cas9 approach needs to be further investigated for the reactivation potentials of nondividing neurons. In both studies, not all cells targeted with CRISPR-Cas9 went through the correction, probably due to inefficiencies in the delivery of these multiplexes into cells and limitations in targeting of the complex to the *FMR1* gene. Furthermore, neither team was able to confirm that these procedures worked in an animal model and no proof was provided that the curation actually caused the neurons behave normally. Still, these studies were essential in showing that the gene can be targeted and cured in patient cells using this protocol.

It was the first time to in vivo analyze ex vivo edited iPSCs engrafted neurons [69]. A dCas9 was fused to Tet1 (an enzyme that catalyzes demethylation of cytosines) to produce a methylation eraser (dCas9-Tet1). The *FMR1* stayed transcriptionally active, and the hyperactive firing rate phenotypes were savaged. The edited neurons expressed the gene *Fragile X Messenger Ribonucleoprotein (FMRP)* for 3 months after transplantation. Furthermore, when dCas9-Tet1 and gRNAs designed to target the CGG repeats were transferred into iPSCs with lentivirus (LV), epigenetic alterations occurred at the FMR1 site. These results confirmed the usefulness of targeting epigenetic-editors to the CGG repeat site. Whether a permanently active dCas9-Tet1 is needed for long-term reactivation at the *FMR1* site remains a critical question.

The introduction of epigenome editing with DNA-targeting tools such as CRISPR-Cas9 has revolutionized the manipulation of gene expression in living cells and organisms.[70] Epigenetic engineering of iPSC-originated neurons was found to be less effective than in iPSCs: levels of restored FMR1 mRNA were 45% that of unedited neurons, and a 20% reduction in CpG methylation at the FMR1 promoter was accomplished after editing. These differences could be due to the technical limitations of separating the edited neurons or differences in the methods of demethylation between different cell types. In an attempt to answer the question: Why do some cells carrying a fragile X mutation remain unaffected and keep producing FMRP? Researchers [59] developed a new GE tool that allows other types of fragile X cells to delete the CGG repeats, too. Embryonic fragile X cells can look unaffected and express *FMR1* when grown in a specific medium. It was discovered that two drugs in the culture media were responsible. These two drugs stimulate demethylating enzymes, which take the methyl tags and return *FMR1* expression in stem cells and neural progenitors originating from people with fragile X. It was realized that the CRISPR-based strategy and the demethylation activity can both trigger DNA to form a structure called an R-loop.[59] These loops arise when the DNA's double strand becomes disturbed by a segment of ssRNA. A large number of CGG repeats in the fragile X cells stabilize this genomic 'Pump', activating a cell's DNA repair mechanisms, which eliminate repeats. To overcome this, researchers designed a

catalytically inactive form of CRISPR that specifically provokes CGG repeats to form R-loops. The catalytically inactive version of CRISPR is smaller than the typical one, making its delivery to the brain easier. However, before any conclusion can be made, it will be important to confirm that R-loops can cause repeat excision in the non-dividing cells.

An RNP complex, a cocktail of sgRNA and purified Cas9 protein, was used to target both the upstream and downstream flanking region of CGG repeats in human fibroblast cell lines having the premutation allele.[71] The results confirmed that this CRISPR system worked successfully in vitro. But it was not possible to remove the repeats in human fibroblast cells, probably because of the low editing efficacy of sgRNA2 that was intended to target the downstream of the CGG repeats.

In 2018, the first in vivo GE in animal models of FXCS was reported.[72] This strategy assessed both Cas9 and Cas12a for their efficacy to KO gene expression in vivo in mice. The nucleases were transported to specific areas of the brain utilizing gold nanoparticles with editing in neurons, astrocytes, and microglia proved to reduce reporter gene expression. In another GE method to target *FMR1*, the *metabotropic glutamate receptor 5* (mGluR5) encoding gene was targeted for KO with Cas9 in the striatum of *FMR1* KO mice.[72] The *Grm5* was selected for targeting because of the excess activation of mGluR5-dependent signaling known in FXCS. Repression in this signaling pathway led to a rescue of the phenotype considered measures of hyperactivity. The authors proposed that although clinical trials that utilized drugs to decrease mGluR5 activity were unsatisfying, applying CRISPR to target the overactivation may be more efficient. The CRISPR/Cas9-mediated technique may also be useful for other diseases resulting from abnormal methylation, such as facioscapulohumeral muscular dystrophy, as well as imprinting diseases.

Remarkably, the delivery strategy caused a focused treatment region, which is required when knocking out a key controller of plasticity. However, the approach has limitations if multiple areas or a large region of the brain have to be edited for therapeutic purposes, a vital concern in translating from mice to humans. Of note, gold nanoparticles have been found to have cellular toxicity at elevated or repeated doses.[73] It is hoped that the GE by transient expression of Cas9 (as RNP) will allow for the consideration of a broad delivery options for therapeutic uses. With the optimization of an appropriate delivery system and a suitable evaluation of specificity, scientists can clinically translate previous studies for the therapeutic editing, particularly in the fragile X-associated disorders.

3.6. Prader-Willis Syndrome

Prader-Willi syndrome (PWS) is a genetic disease that is characterized by a microdeletion of a section of chromosome 15, and consequently a loss of function of genes located on that section locus.[74] These deletions cannot be identified by conventional light microscopy or other traditional methodologies, but can now be visualized by the FISH technique. The mode of inheritance of PWS is complex due to a phenomenon known as genomic imprinting. Typically, both copies of chromosome 15 (one from each parent) are functional in the body's cells. However, in PWS, one copy of this chromosome is absent or inactive, and only the other copy is active. The exact copy that is active depends on whether the disorder is inherited from the father or the mother. The syndrome is initiated by 4-Mb microdeletions and consequently the absence of expression of paternally inherited imprinted genes on a specific region of chromosome 15 (15q11.2-q13.3),[75] though the maternal allele is unharmed but epigenetically silenced.[74] This region has several genes that regulate appetite and metabolism. The main gene implicated is called *Small Nuclear Ribonucleoprotein N* (*SNRPN*). Though the exact genetic basis that leads to PWS remains uncertain, patient mutation profiles have associated the *small nucleolar RNA (snoRNA)* gene *SNORD116* downstream of the SNURF-SNRPN open reading frame inside 15q11-13 as a likely primary cause of the disease.[76][77] However, an atypical 78-kb microdeletion traversing only *SNRPN* exons 2 and 3 and preserving *SNORD116* expression in a patient with a typical PWS phenotype has also been reported. This suggests that loss of *SNORD116* expression may not be required to elicit classic PWS symptoms.[78]

Using a modified CRISPR, a team of biomedical engineers [74] detected and activated a major epigenetic key to turn on the silenced PWS region of maternal chromosome 15 (Figure 5). These genes are found, but silent, in all PWS patients. By restoring the expression of these genes by epigenome editing, researchers corrected the underlying genetic alterations that caused PWS. Nuclease-deactivated Cas9 editing can put chromatin alterations in a highly specific manner, [79,80] allowing for precise assessment of the link between chromatin alterations and gene expression.[80][81][82] These technologies can identify the distal gene controlling elements by pooled gRNA screens, [83,84] defining key controlling elements that are otherwise challenging to forecast.[85][86] In addition to mapping the regulatory landscape in the human genome, these studies serve to identify potential drug targets for next-generation epigenetic therapies. These tools have been applied to recognize regulatory elements of the imprinted 15q11-13 position that is implicated in PWS.[74]

Source: Adapted from [74]

Figure 5 The PWS on human chromosome 15q13.3 is shown. PWS patients with rare paternal microdeletions have defined the critical region over *SNORD116*. Epigenetic editing activates imprinted PWS. dCas9: Nuclease-deactivated Cas9; iPSCs: Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells; M: Maternal; P: Parental; PWS: Prader-Willi Syndrome

Since the maternal copy of chromosome 15q11.2-q13.3 remains unharmed but epigenetically silenced, activation of the maternal allele through the inhibition of epigenetic modifying enzymes and transcription factors offers a therapeutic chance to return the expression of PWS-related genes. [87] However, small molecule-mediated suppression of epigenetic changers carries the risk of OTEs due to the overall loss of crucial gene regulation enzymes, given their prevalent expression and association with numerous loci.[88]

Although this work is still a way from a CRISPR-based gene therapy for PWS becoming a reality, it is an important landmark in understanding how to control gene expression in the PWS region. More studies will be necessary to confirm that gene activation in animal models or human cells can efficiently correct the phenotypic effects and improve clinical results. Future work must focus on directly going for epigenome editing in neurons to return PWS gene expression to understand the relationship between PWS gene expression and PWS-associated neurological phenotypes.

3.7. Williams Syndrome

Williams syndrome (WS), or Williams–Beuren syndrome, is a rare autosomal dominant disorder. [89] It is not usually inherited from parents, but rather it commonly originates from a change in the number of chromosomes because of a random mutation during gametogenesis. This syndrome results from deletion of 1.55 Mb to 1.8 Mb on chromosome 7q11.23, impacting 25-28 genes, including *ELN*, *GTF2I*, *GTF2IRD1*, and *LIMK1*. [89] Of these genes, the functions of only a few genes have been elucidated. [90] However, these genes are vital for the growth of many tissues in the body. Previous research focused on knowing the functions that individual genes contained by the copy-number variation region might be performing in the WS phenotypes. The *Elastin (ELN)* gene is important in the generation of connective tissue and cardiovascular function. Similarly, the *general transcription factor II-1 repeat domain-containing protein 1 (GTF2IRD1)* gene is responsible for producing facial features. Additionally, *LIMK1*, encoding LIM domain kinase 1, is associated with poor visuospatial cognitive deficits observed in WS. [91]

Unlike monogenic diseases, microdeletion disorders such as WS provide specific challenges that relate to the bulky size of the elements to be delivered and the diaphanous number of locations where the genes would need to be targeted to change related phenotypes. The genotype of cells having CRISPR-Cas9-produced heterozygous deletions in Neutrophil *Cytosolic Factor 1* (*NCF1*) gene locus, which is challenged by frequent incidence of chromosomal deletions and pseudogene loci, is similar to the genotype existing in patients with WS.[92] *NCF1* is accompanied on chromosome 7 by two almost identical non-processed pseudogenes, *NCF1B* and *NCF1C*, which have a two-nucleotide GT deletion mutation also in healthy individuals. A Pseudogene-related disorder, the immunodeficiency p47^{phox}-deficient chronic granulomatous disease (p47^{phox} CGD), was corrected utilizing CRISPR-Cas9 to target mutated *NCF1*. [92] Hemizygosity of the *ELN* gene has been connected to connective-tissue abnormalities and hypertension. Though WS is generally not thought of as a cancer-predisposing disorder, existing reports associate the reduced copy number of the *BCL7B* gene, which is located between *NCF1B* and *NCF1*, with blood malignancies such as mature B-Leukemia [93] and Burkitt Lymphoma.[94]

Williams Syndrome Transcription Factor (WSTF) is an important factor in both O⁶-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase (MGMT) deficient and proficient glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) cell lines for response against temozolomide (TMZ) chemotherapy.[95] The loss of WSTF results in a significantly raised TMZ sensitivity in clinically related concentrations for all the studied cell lines. Continuing studies are exploring the underlying mechanisms and possible changes in the DNA damage response pathway caused by WSTF KO.

Although the capacity to detect and modify target genes, either in utero or in initial postnatal stages, provides the potential to develop precise treatment in WS to a great extent, much work is needed before this approach becomes a reality. In the future, therapies are anticipated based on individual genes or routes that are known to be significant for influencing phenotype in WS. Studies in mouse models, for instance, indicate that anti-miRNAs (e.g., anti-miR29a) may be valuable for increasing elastin deposition [96] and that inducing smooth muscle cell behavior through inhibitors of Mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) [97] or integrin β 3 [98] could expand the vascular features of WS. In addition, patient-derived iPSCs may soon provide platforms by which new therapeutics for impact on exclusive WS transcriptional pathways and phenotypes are tested. Initial studies integrating this technology have been utilized to screen for medications that affect the increased smooth muscle cell propagation seen in WS.[99]

3.8. Cri-du-Chat Syndrome

Cri du chat syndrome (CdCS) originates from a heterozygous deletion of a part of the short arm of chromosome 5 (5p-). As implied by the name, children with this abnormality are classically characterized by a cat-like cry; however, they usually lose this feature during the first two years of life.[100] Variances in the sizes of deletions in this chromosomal region are likely behind some of the variations in CdCS, but it commonly affects multiple genes, including *Catenin delta-2S* (*CTNND2*) and *Telomerase reverse transcriptase* (*TERT*). Mutations in *CTNND2* can affect neural development and potentially influence immune system interactions through neural-immune system communication pathways.[101]

Currently, research associated with immunodeficiency-associated CdCS is ongoing. Genetic studies such as Genome Sequencing (WGS) and CRISPR GE are being focused on to better understand the particular genetic deletions on chromosome 5p and their impacts on the immune system. Despite an increase in understanding of exact pathogenic mechanisms, carrying out disease-modifying treatments for CdCS has resulted in limited success.

Recently, it has been revealed that early gene replacement therapy by AAV-*CTNND2* relieves cognitive impairments in CdCS rats, emphasizing the potential for early intervention.[102] However, the efficiency of this therapy is restricted to the early developmental phases and does not completely relieve all CdCS symptoms. These findings expanded the understanding of CdCS pathogenesis and propose hopeful therapeutic directions. The genomic resemblance between rats and humans implies that modeling CdCS in rats could provide a more relevant avenue. Therefore, an urgent demand emerges to build up a rat model that faithfully replicates the principal pathogenic mechanisms driving CdCS, using the precision of CRISPR-Cas9 GE technology. In fact, a fruitful rat model that accurately reflects a prevalent genetic abnormality found in CdCS has been presented.[102] This success is attained through accurate genetic deletion in the matching region, leading to a rat model covering a comprehensive array of CdCS-related traits. These traits correspond to those observed in genuine CdCS patients. The engineered CdCS rat model allowed for widespread *CTNND2* expression within the animal brain since the AAV vector overcomes the blood-brain barrier. The outcome is a robust adjustment of deficiencies in both cognitive function and social behavior, compelling and unequivocally underscoring the significant potential embedded in gene replacement therapy for CdCS.

3.9. Angelman Syndrome

Angelman syndrome (AS) is a rare genetic disorder produced by a microdeletion of the maternally originated chromosome 15 (15q12) in about 70% of cases.[22] Most conditions of AS are not inherited and happen sporadically, which means they are not passed down from the parents. However, in some situations, the disorder can be inherited from a parent who carries a mutation in the *Ubiquitin-protein ligase E3A (UBE3A)* gene, which controls synaptic development, or another gene that is implicated in the imprinting process.

Gene therapy is specifically suitable for rare diseases such as AS because they usually have a very distinct genetic cause. But the challenge is that almost 95% of rare genetic diseases have no available treatment or intervention options. The CRISPR-based GE technology has been utilized to rapidly build up in vivo and in vitro models to explain the pathogenetic mechanisms of AS and to diseases and to find potential treatments. To facilitate the study on how the deletion of *UBE3A* in vitro and in vivo (rat) models was produced by knocking down *UBE3A* utilizing CRISPR. *UBE3A*-deficient rats displayed signs similar to those that have been noticed in patients with AS, specifically cognitive and motor impairment.[103] Nerve cells lacking functional *UBE3A* lose the capacity to fire mature action potentials.[104] By silencing *UBE3A*, CRISPR has assisted in pinpointing the genetic control of neural circuits and the causative gene for AS. However, the CRISPR/Cas9 strategy has to be further tested for its safety and efficiency before advancing to clinical trials.

3.10. Wolff-Hirschhorn Syndrome

Wolf-Hirschhorn syndrome (WHS) is a rare segmental aneuploidy syndrome caused by a partial 4p deficiency (4p-). Individuals with WHS have variable-sized short arms of chromosome 4 deletion, ranging from less than 2 Mb up to 30 Mb, and always including the band 4p16. However, WHS phenotype could also be produced by complex chromosomal rearrangements, such as ring chromosomes or translocations.[105] The WHS minimal critical region (WHSMCR) is found about 2 Mb from the telomere 4p, within band 4p16.3 (a zone of 200–750 kb in genes—*WHSC1*, *LETM1*, *NSD2*, *CPLX1*, and *PIGG* being often deleted).[106]

It has been discovered that WHS-connected DNA methylation signatures are reliant on *nuclear receptor binding SET domain protein 2 (NSD2)* dysfunction,[107] and could be valuable in identifying *NSD2* variants of uncertain significance. Apparently, *NSD2* loss-of-function variants resulted in a discrete, rather mild phenotype partly overlapping with WHS. [108] Furthermore, chromosomal microarray revealed all currently known deletions of the WHS and can verify if the deletion is pure or a fraction of a more complex rearrangement.[105]

Preliminary data indicate that the craniofacial and neuroanatomical phenotypes are attributed to the dose imbalance of several genes located in the 4p16.1.[109] There are no previous reports in the published literature regarding the application of CRISPR GE technology in the *WHSMCR* genes. The question asked is: Whether the same transcripts might be relevant to the deletion by inducing deletions in each of *WD Repeat Domain 1 (WDR1)* and *Cytokine-dependent hematopoietic cell linkerS (CLNK)* orthologs by CRISPR/Cas9? It has been stated that the reactivated clonal lines after CRISPR editing had reduced methylation levels at the CpG locations. [68] For the chromosome-mediated strategies, CRISPR-based gene therapy technologies are being explored in WHS, like other rare conditions.

4. Discussion

The international research on the CRISPR-Cas system has revolutionized our understanding of molecular biology. The application of CRISPR-Cas9-based GE technologies is widening our knowledge of the treatment of diseases. Active research is currently being carried out to explore the opportunities for treatment and prevention of inherited and acquired genetic disorders. CRISPR/Cas9-mediated technology has the potential to treat a broad spectrum of human tumors and even aneuploidy syndromes, such as trisomics: DS, KS, and monosomics like TS or segmental aneuploidy syndromes, for example, AS, CdCS, PWS, WHS, and WS.

The successful use of the CRISPR GE tool to delete or silence an entire additional chromosome copy represents a striking scientific advance. Remarkably, after the additional chromosome was removed, the corrected cells displayed normalized gene function—an unprecedented outcome in chromosomal disorder research. Scientists have illuminated the track, and the potential for curing at the genuine genetic level is currently within reach. Though the CRISPR research operated in a lab setting represents a landmark step toward curing chromosomal disorders, the clinical applications are years away because several mechanistic questions have to be answered. Before the clinical applications, the methods could be tested in vivo in animal models and adapted to become a keystone for future cell-replacement therapies. Challenges and limitations have to be addressed by geneticists, bioethicists, and policymakers before human translation.

Key Limitations

Although the CRISPR/Cas toolbox for treating chromosomal disorders may become an important area of future investigation, it includes key challenges that must be addressed for clinical applications. These limitations can be summarized as follows:

The first major challenge is how to selectively target one of two or three chromosomes, and the molecular and cellular characteristics, such as location, function, gene expression, etc. In accordance with these desirable process considerations, possible gene therapy for chromosomal disorders ranges from downregulation of inhibitory miRNAs and transcriptional activation by ZFNs, TALENs, or CRISPR-Cas9 technology.

A critical practical limitation of the CRISPR/Cas9-mediated method is how to induce multiple DNA cuts efficiently. Also, the efficacy of chromosome deletion differs among diverse repeat sequences, and it is not easy to predict whether these repetitive sequences “work well”. In addition, only a few cell types tolerate huge chromosome-scale deletions. Cells from non-inbred species like humans may behave in unpredictable and unphysiological modes when a whole chromosome becomes haploid following a chromosomal deletion. Although the dCas9-based methods are attractive for evading DSBs, which may lead to unanticipated key genomic changes,[110] they cannot control whether to gain or lose the target chromosomes. Unanticipated endonuclease activity is noticed at the nontarget allele even after the target chromosome is lost. Thus, defending nontarget alleles from Cas9-induced DSBs.[35] These issues may be tackled by epigenomic methods that do not cause DSBs.

When the target chromosome is not deleted by Cas9 treatment, alternatives are established in the remaining target chromosome, and critically, the target genome is substituted by a sequence no longer identifiable by the employed gRNA.[35] The failure of removal of the extra chromosome may result from off-target editing, which potentially affects unintended genomic loci. Although scientists did not detect evident off-target mutations or chromosome rearrangements in the chromosome-removed cell lines and mice,[23] it will be necessary to evaluate potential OTEs before CRISPR/Cas9-based chromosome deletion could be used clinically.

The therapeutic translation of CRISPR-Cas9 relies on mitigating nuclease promiscuity through elevated-fidelity alternatives and chemical guide modifications.[111] To enhance the specificity of the target nucleic acid, the CRISPR protein is modified, and an efficient delivery mode of the CRISPR-Cas system is used to minimize the off-target problems.[112] Base editors (BEs) provide a way to edit single nucleotides without running the danger of causing DSB-induced toxicity. Still, base editing faces some of the similar challenges already mentioned for CRISPR systems, including OTEs, more so with Cytosine BEs than Adenine BEs.[113] Moreover, base editing is restricted by its packaging by viral vectors due to the large size of BEs.[114] As an alternative strategy that avoids the potential off-target problems, it has been stated that iPSC reprogramming possibly corrects structural and numerical chromosomal anomalies. [53]

The previous studies [35] concentrated on subtelomere targeting and without insight into how focusing on other chromosomal zones and their combinations, such as peri-centromeric and centromeric regions, affects chromosome exclusion efficacy. Also, they were limited by the usage of only two cell types (iPS cell line and skin fibroblasts). The experiments provided proof-of-concept for the “Trisomic rescue” strategy. Assessing this approach in clinically related cell types, like neurons and glial cells, would significantly promote its ability for translational applications. In addition, the WGS analysis was not made on cells after all treatments.[35] Thus, comprehensive data on genome alterations across all cells utilized in these investigations may not be enough.

The restrictions associated with the delivery of the editing components. Most of the Cas proteins are large molecular weight proteins (~4.2 kb), limiting the CRISPRs to the size of the carrier viral genes.[115] To overcome this difficulty, researchers have to develop low molecular weight CRISPR orthologs or split-Cas systems, which usually compromise activity or specificity [111]. Researchers have responded to this obstacle by using nonviral inventions such as lipid nanoparticles (LNP), gold NPs, and polymeric carriers. These modalities offer promise for the transient delivery of Cas RNP complexes and reducing OTEs. However, attaining tissue-specific targeting, endosomal evasion, and effective cellular uptake remains an obstacle to robust *in vivo* editing.[116]

Overcoming immunological barriers to bacterial nucleases and optimizing delivery means is important for clinical-grade uses. Improvements of the CRISPR tool, the efficacy of the CRISPR-Cas system must be enhanced to reduce the immune response. It was indicated [117] that more than 50% of the human subjects had preexisting anti-Cas9 antibodies against the most commonly used Cas9 orthologs. The use of the immunogenic epitope-engineered Cas9 orthologs with decreased antigenicity and inducible anti-CRISPR modules reduces virus-associated immunogenic problems and progressively regulates editing.[118] To confront immunogenicity, researchers have investigated

humanized and engineered Cas orthologs with diminished antigenicity. For example, Cas12a from *Acidaminococcus* sp. shows distinct PAM requirements and reduced immunogenicity.

Another potential use of the CRISPR technology would be to model evolutionary changes to chromosome. This is, in particular, a significant ethical issue regarding human genome alterations. With somatic editing, any possible risk would be enclosed within the individual after informed consent to participate in the therapy. These considerations have led to debate over both pros and cons, emphasizing the monetary cost, efficacy, access to this resource, and the need to create regulating legislation.[119]

On one hand, some people believe that chromosomal disorders are quite life-threatening and also quality-of-life-destroying. CRISPR is just a practice of splicing genetic code into a gene (or in the case of trisomy, cutting up an extra chromosome). This CRISPR treatment most likely would be a technique done in the womb (during fetal development) can't change DNA after the child has been born. On the other hand, critics believe CRISPR is "evil" since embryonic editing not only eliminates autonomy in the decision-making process of the later-born people, but also allows unpredictable and permanent side effects to be passed down through generations. Other opponents argue that many people with DS wouldn't consider it a "disease" or necessarily a death sentence; they need to be "fixed". So, the prospect of human GE will probably become a conflict between the government and citizens about the issues of ethics, patient rights, and medical "freedom". Still, some other people imagine the CRISPR/Cas9-mediated chromosome elimination approach being applied in conjunction with gene drives, as deletion of the Y chromosome could result in the disappearance of males and collapse of mosquito populations that command global attention with remarkable consistency.

Regulatory barriers (and bans) to achieving CRISPR's hopes. The reported breakthrough in GE technology-mediated trisomy rescue was achieved in vitro (in the lab) and is still far from being approved for application in humans. Among these approaches, KaryoCreate a recently reported advanced chromosome eradication technique using the dCas9 system is incapable of targeting a chromosome; for example, chromosome 21, due to the absence of particular repetitive sequences in the pericentromeric region proper for gRNA design.[120]

Multiple regulatory obstacles stand between the appealing technology and its widespread clinical application. Governmental organizations in many countries are forbidden from financing embryonic editing research, restricting researchers to private funding.[121]

5. Conclusion and Implications for Future

Earlier studies focused on the outcomes of karyotype correction by chromosome deletion without sufficiently addressing the factors defining chromosome repair versus loss. More studies will be necessary to add a temporal dimension, i.e., comprehending how genomics change during development. The directions of the next investigations have to stress understanding how Cas9-handled chromosome s are lost and the results of Cas9-cured chromosome left in the genome.

Previous work was restricted to the manipulations of only iPS cells and skin fibroblasts. In the future, research must intensify the study of clinically related cell types, like neurons and glial cells, before applying CRISPR in clinical trials. Also, future studies should investigate the effect of genes involved in the DSB repair machinery on the degree of chromosome excision.

Another potential option in the future could be editing the disease-causing genes of an affected fetus in utero, where embryos are produced, and then CRISPR GE is deployed to eliminate the genetic mutation from affected preimplanted embryos. Following this, the edited embryos are implanted. But uses of CRISPR/Cas9 on human embryos are still largely hypothetical.

Finally, prospective parents may in the future be able to choose CRISPR's somatic therapeutic intervention for a diseased child postnatally (after birth). Procedures to achieve somatic GE applying CRISPR in children or adults are divided into two groups: ex vivo and in vivo. The ex vivo treatments are the most likely to become a significant option for expectant parents in the near future. Ex vivo GE involves separating a patient's cells, correcting them in culture, and then transfusing edited cells back into the patient. Today, there are several labs around the world working with CRISPR on Usher's Syndrome, a condition that causes loss of vision and hearing. Applying such radical genetic interventions to living organisms imposes risks that need to be carefully examined.

The human germline editing for therapeutic purposes continues to be highly controversial. It is ethically unfavorable in its current state, and its debates may not be considered until enough long-term research on the ongoing somatic CRISPR therapy clinical trials is conducted. Extensive research on chromosome editing in live rodents and nonhuman primates is needed to test potential “treatments” for all kinds of conditions in humans. While they may be years away from obtaining any kind of approval by the FDA or Ethics committees for examining human subjects

Advocates for people with chromosomal syndromes emphasize that this revolution should not be viewed as a quest to “eradicate” individuals with these conditions, but rather as a means to offer families more options and improve quality of life. If some therapy for a genetic disorder is available, why not do it to prevent suffering? There is no human ugliness in using this technology. There is neither “eugenics” nor religious “evil” going on.

Compliance with ethical standards

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